

Impact of Using Analytic Rubrics for Peer Assessment on EFL Students' Writing Performance: An Experimental Study

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Abstract

To develop the English competence of Vietnamese people, many changes have been made in the education system in the context of Vietnam, and one of them is changing teaching and assessment methods. Peer assessment is recommended as a potential assessment method to help learners develop their writing ability. This experimental study was conducted to test whether training learners to use analytic rubrics for peer assessment helps them develop their writing skills/ performance. The intervention was conducted in a university setting with the participation of 22 students. The results showed a significant difference in the students' writing performance before and after the intervention. It showed that the intervention positively impacted their writing performance, especially the way they developed ideas and used words and grammar structures. However, in-depth interviews showed that learners with sufficient writing performance before participating in the intervention did not develop much, or even their writing performance was negatively affected. The implications are drawn and presented in this article.

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Introduction

In the context of integration into the global economy, English as the international language plays a significant role in the orientation of innovation and development in each country in general and Vietnam in particular. In Vietnam, since education is considered a priority policy, employing English communicatively and professionally is crucially necessary (Thao & Mai, 2020). However, teaching and learning English as a foreign language (EFL) has encountered various challenges. Even though some improvements have been made in the national education system so far, teaching and learning English is still reported to be ineffective (Thao & Mai, 2020). As a result, educators have made endless efforts to find more feasible and enhanced EFL teaching methods. In that case, constant changes have been made for the improvement of the education system, such as the movement from a teacher-centered approach to a learner-centered approach (Nghia et al., 2020), retraining of English teachers' proficiency via the National Foreign Language 2020 Project (Nguyen, 2018), enhancement in methodological language teaching as well as adaptation of new learning materials or textbooks and so on.

Nevertheless, because of the long-time influence of traditional language teaching and learning approaches, several challenges seem unavoidable. Alternatively, in the series of such challenges of English language teaching and learning, classroom assessment is one of the most severe problems. In the study by Tran (2015), using English communicatively and professionally is still an enormous challenge for English learners in Vietnam, although much effort has been made to enhance the target language teaching. Importantly, one of the five main reasons is related to assessment and curriculum (Tran, 2015). Vietnamese education seemingly concentrate too much on giving students' learning summative assessment through exams, especially the final ones. Moreover, English tests are mainly concerned with lexical and grammatical knowledge with little real-life language use, which resulted in "the lack of consistency in EFL assessment criteria set by higher education (HE) and also a lack of alignment between assessment practices and the objectives of EFL education at tertiary level" affecting the validity of assessment results (Tran, 2015, p.11). In addition, Ho (2015) provided that teacher-centered teaching is still dominant in Vietnam. The shortcomings in English assessment practice in the nation include outdated assessment methods, lack of reliability and validity, and teaching and learning to the tests (Ho, 2015). As a solution, the Ministry of Education and Training (MOET) made important decisions on assessment changes. Formative assessment is a potential tendency of judgment though it is still not paid much attention to in the Vietnamese context (Tran, 2015).

Many previous studies have been conducted to ensure the potential of formative assessment. Particularly, formative assessment is a potential solution to improve teaching and learning processes (Widiastuti&Saukah, 2017). According to Ahmed and Troudi (2018), formative assessment tends to be used as an assessment form for generating feedback on students' performance to improve and accelerate their learning. It is described as any assessment designed to explore learners' strengths and weaknesses in their learning to effect remedial action

(Ahmed & Troudi, 2018). It is to inform that formative assessments can be critical in empowering the learner and enhancing classroom learning. It mainly aims to facilitate teachers to conduct more suitable teaching and learning works to enhance students' learning achievement.

Consequently, formative assessment can be used to determine and modify learning activities and provides the most appropriate strategies to improve students' learning results. Accordingly, more and more teachers use formative assessment alongside traditional forms of test papers, credits, exams, etc. (Widiastuti & Saukah, 2017). It can be conducted daily in language classrooms by teachers during their teaching process so that they can do immediate revision and organize teaching and learning activities to improve student's learning outcomes. In addition, there has been a shift from teacher-centered instruction to communicative and student-centered instruction and the emergence of a range of new assessment approaches (Radford, 2014). Consequently, formative assessment emerges as one vital contribution to the teaching and learning English by global language teachers and learners.

On the other hand, in Vietnam, English teaching and learning assessment is also confronted with problems. In particular, most EFL teachers find that teaching English writing skills is a complicated process and seriously impacts the learning outcomes of target language learners in the context of Vietnam (Nguyen, 2009). In current language classrooms, Vietnamese EFL teachers have to face a range of questions, including "how to make EFL students aware of why they should write in English, how to teach students to write, how to give feedback to students' writing, and how to assess students' writing skill" (Nguyen, 2009, p. 61). According to Birjandi and Siyyari (2010), alternative means of assessment are considered the most effective for meeting the goals of educational assessment. Using checklists, videotapes, audiotapes, teacher observations, journals, logs, conferences, portfolios, self-assessments, and peer assessments are all possible means of alternative assessment (Birjandi & Siyyari, 2010). Alternatively, in the study by Ahmed and Troudi (2018), peer assessment is a beneficial form of formative assessment for practice in writing courses in terms of judging, evaluating, and considering the qualities of one's academic work or abilities. In short, peer assessment (PA) is a potential approach for facilitating student essay writing enhancement in such current research.

Razi (2015) stated that writing academic papers is a sophisticated task for students, and their assessment process is also a challenge for language teachers. The author emphasized that assessing writing outnumbers the solutions. In consequence, after referring to a range of theoretical approaches, Razi (2015) found that using a scoring rubric is an effective way to evaluate "various discourse and linguistic features along with specific rules of academic writing" (p. 1). According to Allen (2014), rubrics provide raters with criteria for assessing students' work. They can be used to evaluate almost any product, such as essays, research reports, portfolios, works of art, recitals, oral presentations, performances, and group activities. They effectively "clarify expectations to students, providing formative feedback, grading students, and/or assessing courses and programs" (Allen, 2014, p. 1). More importantly, judgments could be made by students themselves or by others, including faculty, other students, fieldwork supervisors, and external reviewers. In brief, it is somehow promising to use analytic rubrics for students' peer assessment of their written works. However, not much research has been done to verify this. Therefore, this study attempted to address the issues surrounding the impact of training students to use analytic rubrics for peer assessment on their writing performance.

Literature Review

Analytic Rubrics

A rubric with clear criteria is always considered an effective tool in assessing learners' works, both in oral and written forms (Allen, 2014). Different researchers variously defined its terminology. Expressly, Çetin (2011) referred to rubrics as a scoring tool for grading assignments. The author is convinced that rubrics provided "a point-by-point guide" to help raters analyze and determine an overall score for a given text. With a range of points for each category, a rater could easily follow to assess the body of a written work. The expert restated previous findings of other researchers that using rubrics could make writing assessments more reliable and professional (Jonsson & Svingby, 2007; Silvestri & Oescher, 2006). In line with this, rubrics can assess students' writing more objectively and address the problems of time constraints or lack of personnel to become a widely-used tool to score students' essays. Additionally, a rubric is also defined as a scoring guide with criteria employed to differentiate the levels of performance in evaluating students' work. According to the aforementioned studies, rubrics can be utilized to assess student performance, such as course assignments, exams, practice and internships, research papers, portfolios, group projects, public presentations, and many other types of work. Every element of student performance is evaluated quickly with detailed subscales set in the rubric, and scores can be gathered conveniently into overall results for further analysis. Consequently, a rubric is virtually helpful in assessing students' works in general or written products in particular.

Generally, despite some similarities between the two scoring scales, holistic rubrics differed from analytic ones. The body of work was assessed as a whole, and many parts were not broken up to be scored individually, so the final score was the summation of collective individual scores (Çetin, 2011). In contrast, detailed guides for assessing analytic scales helped clarify the skill level in various areas of written expression. Çetin (2011) informed that the holistic rubric used a single score to rate determined properties of students' written works, but

levels of performance were evaluated superficially, such as grammar, spelling, and punctuation errors (Beyreli& Ari, 2009). As a result, teachers might reward not-well-performed writing with a high score under the impact of the writing's prominent properties even though it was possibly not worth it or vice versa. Beyreli and Ari (2009) said that holistic rubrics have some limitations in obtaining complete and correct student data. This method is not as well as expected, particularly for developing students with low or medium-level performance. The difficulty of preparation of a holistic rubric is distinguishing a level from another when all properties are listed.

On the contrary, the analytic rubric was preferred by numerous language teachers due to its multiple scales and collection of scores offered over a performance instead of only one. For example, a three-section-and-ten-property study conducted by Beyreli and Ari (2009) on using analytic rubrics in assessing writing performance verified the usefulness of multiple scales and scoring guides of an analytic rubric. Its complexity represented external structure (format, spelling, and punctuation), language and expression (vocabulary, sentences, paragraphs, and expression), and organization (title, introduction, story, and conclusion). Scoring scales by an analytic rubric were typically more consistent and specific to areas of students' growth though it might take more time to develop. Accordingly, Ayhan and Türkyılmaz (2015) quoted a list of analytic rubrics' advantages stated as follows: They provide valuable feedback to learners on areas of strength and weakness; their dimensions can be weighted to reflect relative importance; and they can show learners that they have made progress over time in some or all dimensions when the same rubric categories are used repeatedly.

In writing, utilizing analytic rubrics usefully helped to determine students' proficiency levels and significantly enhanced the quality of their written pieces via scoring feedback and self-correction (Çetin, 2011). Via applying shared score sets in analytic rubrics to analyze samples' sub-skills in each student's written product, component's parts (handwriting, sentences, title, etc.) constituting the writing were separately evaluated to determine whether they are necessary to be included or not (Beyreli& Ari, 2009). Despite taking time to develop or adapt, analytic scoring is wider, more comprehensive, and useful. Both teachers and students could profit from using such assessment tools because teachers were likely to comprehend what score they assessed for which specific property thanks to detailed criteria, while students were able to create a quality text according to criteria specified if they knew these. Analytic scoring could guide teachers, and students could orient their writing activities. Crehan (1997) added that teachers beneficially know their learners' current situation and thus possibly assist students in determining solid and weak aspects in their writings through orderly and comprehensive feedback (Beyreli& Ari, 2009). The analytic rubric was likely more advantageous than the holistic one and attracted more experts' attention because of its positive aspects.

Nonetheless, target language teachers should not apply analytic rubrics to their teaching and classroom assessments without caution. Analytic scales also contain potential threats, so their unprofessional use may lead to unexpected results (Çetin, 2011). Accordingly, Ayhan and Türkyılmaz (2015) restated analytic rubrics' advantages, encompassing (1) separated artificial points impossibly gave students a good assessment of their whole performance; (2) it took teacher more time to create and use analytic scales; (3) inter- and intra-reliability was hardly reached on all the dimensions in comparison with a holistic scoring guide; and (4) owing to overemphasizing the role of accuracy, raters tended to evaluate grammar related categories more strictly than other categories. In short, analytic rubrics were perhaps potential for classroom assessment, but utilizers need to take careful consideration.

Many researchers seemed inclined to assert the reliability of analytic rubrics more than holistic ones (e.g., Elbow, 2000; Gunning, 2006). Turgut (1990) claimed that the reliability of scoring written products was generally lower due to lacking an agreement on what properties should exist in a composition or written text and not-subjective-criteria assessment. Hence, analytic scoring was a helpful key to raising the harmony among raters and the scores' reliability. It was suggested that the student's writing assessment criteria should be determined through composition, text linguistics, and literature knowledge.

Despite possible negative impacts, analytic rubrics are likely more considerable than holistic scales in assessing learners' writing compositions. In addition, in the current study, the researchers aimed to measure the degree of learners' writing enhancement after a period of time; thus, specific improvements in students' writing characteristics needed to be collected, evaluated, and analyzed. Therefore, an analytic rubric was a more feasible assessment tool.

Peer Assessment

PA has been a movement from a teacher-centered to a student-centered mode of education (Wride, 2017). According to Spiller (2012), it is simply the process in which students provide feedback on the quality of their work. It may include providing feedback, a grade on a product, or performance among learners based on the criteria of excellence for that work. It involves the active engagement of students in their learning, responsibility, metacognitive skills, and a dialogical, collaborative mode of teaching and learning. In such cases, students become assessors in evaluating their performance, which is the kind of highly contextualized learning faced in life and work (Wride, 2017).

On the other hand, a study by Topping (2017) referred to PA as an arrangement in which learners participate in the process of considering the amount, level, value, worth, and quality of success of the products of learnings of

their equal-status peers. PA is emphasized to mediate students to help each other plan their planning, identify their strengths and weaknesses, target areas for remedial action, and develop metacognitive and other personal and professional skills. In this research, PA is comprehended as a process in which learners take part in evaluating and scoring their peers' products in aspects of good essay writing with the assistance of an adopted scoring scale.

Besides, PA is one of the primary and effective forms of age in English teaching and learning. Orienting learners into PA is an unavoidable and necessary tendency in education because a teacher-centered classroom firstly is a global inclination, and PA is a natural extension of such transition into an educational model in which learners would be centered as well as students' active engagement in learning, their responsibility, metacognitive skills and a dialogical, collaborative model of teaching and learning are emphasized (Spiller, 2012). The idea that students practice becoming assessors is a kind of contextualized learning gained in work and life (Wride, 2017). Secondly, according to Nicol et al. (2019), there are considerable evidence of students' deep dissatisfaction with teacher-led feedback practices. Consequently, engaging learners in the assessment process of providing feedback on each other's work can be a feasible solution. Based on assessment criteria for giving feedback, students go deeper into their learning, reflect on learning and then allow the sharing of what new meaning appears (Wride, 2017; Ritonga et al., 2022; Mustafa & Yusuf, 2022).

Furthermore, in terms of promoting the social constructivist models of education, fostering learners' learning cooperation helps re-address the traditional individualistic concept of assessment or the teacher-only assessment concept. PA is a valuable tool for lessening the teaching staff's marking load and taking time for other teaching and learning aspects. It is also an opportunity for teachers to spend time managing the peer assessment process itself more effectively. Alternatively, assessment activities must align with the emphasizing module of peer learning and collaboration. In other words, in order to make the process of students' decision-making on each other's work and establishment of "good work" both appropriate and credible, such evaluation process should be done anonymously, randomly, and individually (Wride, 2017).

PA brings about lots of benefits to the target language teaching and learning. First of all, learners' participation in the process of making judgments is always appreciated by experts because it develops learners' preparation for their subsequent working life (Spiller, 2012). Accordingly, numerous investigations have been conducted by educators to convince positive preeminence of PA, and they virtually come up with a conclusion that peer involvement in assessment is exceptionally advantageous to learners in various aspects. Spiller (2012) strongly agreed and inherited those findings in his study. To begin with, peer learning has been a vital part of the learning process in learners' lives. It is a formal educational practice but lost because of the traditional teacher-centered approach (Boud&Falchikov, 2007).

Moreover, learning from peers positively creates a cooperative learning environment for students, supporting them to establish good work; however, their roles while engaging in peer learning activities need to be a commensurate shift in assessment focus (Spiller, 2012). Thirdly, Kvale (2006) said that as peer learning is a cognitive apprenticeship model, students can help each other fill in their learning gaps from which they comprehend and develop a more sophisticated grasp of the learning process. Then, from peer learning to the assessment process, research evidence indicates the extreme effectiveness of peer feedback in developing students' writing skills. Learners benefit enormously from their classroom partners' comments. In particular, students who comment on their peer's written works self-grow their judging capacity and make intellectual choices, while feedback-receiver ones get a wider range of ideas about their work and promote development and improvement (Kvale, 2006; Ritonga et al., 2022; Mustafa & Yusuf, 2022). Furthermore, not only can students' learning status be enhanced, but teachers' and students' power imbalance is also lessened by peer evaluation. Peer feedback can be paid on the process, encouraging students to clarify, review and edit their ideas. Finally, students need to learn how to receive and give immediate feedback, which is an integral part of most work contexts as they should involve themselves in the active participation of contributing their role to the familiar learning environment through practicing providing feedback to other classmates on the quality of their work (Boud&Falchikov, 2007; Ritonga et al., 2022; Mustafa & Yusuf, 2022).

In short, promoting PA in the language classroom is crucial for target language teachers. Therefore, to maintain and apply PA effectively, Li et al. (2010) proposed that both assessors and those assessees could be anonymous during the scoring process to reduce students' discomfort. This could be a multiple-time process during a module or course so that all students can experience and make the marking more objective. In conclusion, PA is possibly a helpful utensil for developing learners' collaborative learning and a potential alternative assessment form for teachers in language classrooms.

Methods

Research Design

This study used the design of an experimental study to explore the impact of instructing students to use analytic rubrics for peer assessment on their writing performance. With the goal of understanding the impact of an intervention on learners' learning in practice, it can be said that no design can be better than an experimental study.

Participants

Participants in this study included 22 English-major students studying at a well-recognized university in Southwest Vietnam. All students took the same set of writing modules, and the goal of the module was to help students demonstrate a mastery of essay writing on the different topics covered in the program. During this module, students were trained to use analytic rubrics adapted from the study by Jacobs et al. (1981) for peer review. Details of rubrics are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Analytic Rubrics

RUBRICS FOR WRITING PERFORMANCE EVALUATION				
Student:		Date	Topic:	
Writing elements	Score	Level	Criteria	Comments
Content		30-27	Excellent to very good: knowledgeable; substantive; thorough development of writing; relevant to assigned topic	
		26-22	Good to average: some knowledge of topic; adequate range; limited development of writing; mostly relevant to topic, but lacks detail	
		21-17	Fair to poor: limited knowledge of topic; little substance; inadequate development of topic	
		16-13	Very poor: does not show knowledge of topic; non-substance; not pertinent; not enough to evaluate	
Organization		20-18	Excellent to very good: fluent expression; ideas clearly stated/ supported; succinct; well-organized; logical sequencing; cohesive	
		17-14	Good to average: somewhat choppy; loosely organized but main ideas stand out; limited support; logical but incomplete sequencing	
		13-10	Fair to poor: non-fluent; ideas confused or disconnected; lacks logical sequencing and development	
		9-7	Very poor: does not communicate; no organization; or not enough to evaluate	
Vocabulary		20-18	Excellent to very good: sophisticated range; effective word/ idiom choice and usage; word form mastery; appropriate register	
		17-14	Good to average: adequate range; occasional errors of word/ idiom form, choice, usage but meaning not obscured	
		13-10	Fair to poor: limited range; frequent errors of word/ idiom form, choice, usage; meaning confused or obscured	
		9-7	Very poor: essentially translation; little knowledge of English vocabulary, idioms, word form; or not enough to evaluate	
Language use		25-22	Excellent to very good: effective, complex construction; few errors of agreement, tense, number, word order/ function, articles, pronouns, prepositions	
		21-18	Good to average: effective but simple construction; minor problems in complex constructions; several errors of agreement, tense, number, word order/function, articles, pronouns, prepositions but meaning seldom obscured	
		17-11	Fair to poor: major problems in simple/ complex constructions; frequent errors of negation, agreement, tense, number, word order/ function, articles, pronouns, prepositions, and/or fragments, run-ons, deletions; meaning confused	

		or obscured
	10-5	Very poor: virtually no mastery of sentence construction rules; dominated by errors; does not communicate; or not enough to evaluate
Mechanics	5	Excellent to very good: demonstrate mastery of conventions; few errors of spelling, punctuation, capitalization, paragraphing
	4	Good to average: occasional errors of spelling, punctuation, capitalization, paragraphing but meaning not obscured
	3	Fair to poor: frequent errors of spelling, punctuation, capitalization, paragraphing; poor handwriting; meaning confused or obscured
	2	Very poor: no mastery of conventions; dominated by errors of spelling, punctuation, capitalization, paragraphing; handwriting illegible; or not enough to evaluate
Total score:		
Reader:		
Comments:		

According to the rubrics, there are five features in a written text that the graders considered to give scores. Specifically, they are content (30%), organization (20%), vocabulary (20%), language use (25%), and mechanics (5%). Notably, in each feature, there were detailed descriptions of criteria that the users could base on and gave corresponding scores with four different levels consisting of excellent to very good, good to average, fair to poor, and very poor. The score levels were different depending on each feature. For instance, in the content feature, the score ranged down respectively from 30-27 (excellent to very good), 26-22 (good to average), 21-17 (fair to poor), 16-13 (very poor) while in the organization feature, the score ranged down respectively 20-18 (excellent to very good), 17-14 (good to average), 13-10 (fair to poor), 9-7 (very poor). The maximum score for an essay was 100 points. The rubric also included a space for the assessor's comments so that the rater possibly gave feedback to the writer, if any. All students were fully informed about the study, and participation was voluntary. Students can withdraw from the study if the intervention affects their academic, psychological, or other adverse effects.

Ten out of 22 participants were selected based on the mean difference between the pre-test and post-test to participate in the interview. The selection of participants for the interview based on the mean difference contributes to the study of clarifying the impact of the intervention on learners' learning from the perspective of the most successful learners and the least successful learners. Table 2 presents information for interview participants.

Table 2. Information of interviewees

Pseudonyms	Mean-pretest	Mean-posttest	Mean difference
David	75.00	91.00	16.00
Daniel	63.00	74.67	11.67
Brian	69.00	80.00	11.00
Emma	85.33	95.67	10.33
Elizabeth	76.00	86.33	10.33
Jessica	80.33	82.00	1.67
Emily	87.67	88.33	0.67
Christopher	84.67	82.33	-2.33
John	88.00	84.67	-3.33
Jennifer	93.33	87.33	-6.00

Based on the information in Table 2, the successful group consisted of 5 learners, including David, Daniel, Brian, Emma, and Elizabeth, and 5 of the unsuccessful group included Jessica, Emily, Christopher, John, and Jennifer. All names are pseudonyms to avoid affecting learners' personal information.

Data Collection Instruments

The data collection tools in this study were two writing tests used before and after the intervention. The test asks students to write a 250-word essay on a topic in one hour. The requirements of the tests were designed by a research team member who has been teaching writing for more than three years. The structure of the pre-test and post-test was entirely the same, and in the teaching process, all writing tasks were designed according to the

same structure. Furthermore, both tests required students to write on “Music” but differed in content to avoid the students’ memory affecting the test results.

In addition to two tests, the study also used semi-structured interviews with purposefully selected participants. Specifically, the questions used in the interviews focused on revealing students’ perceptions of the impact of using analytic rubrics to assess their peers on their writing performance, especially essay writing. The interview protocol was designed after hours of discussion by the research team. At the same time, the research team consulted with experts in languages with extensive research and publishing experience. Vietnamese was used during the interview process to help interviewers and interviewees answer quickly and accurately. Each interview usually lasts one to one and a half hour in a quiet place to avoid distractions. In addition, before each interview, the research team sent key interview questions via email to interviewees to give them an overview of the interview before it took place. In emails, the research team also asked interviewees for permission that the interview would be recorded for later analysis.

Data Analysis

Data analysis was performed according to the following steps. First, the teacher responsible for teaching in the intervention and two other writing teachers would grade students’ essays. All three teachers used the same analytic rubrics adapted from Jacobs et al. (1981), shown in Figure 1. The pre-test and post-test results of the whole group would be compared to get an overview of the impact of the intervention on students’ writing performance. Furthermore, the results of all five features with the same total score were compared using Pair-Sample t-tests powered by the latest version of SPSS. The difference was considered significant when p-values were less than .05. Next, each student’s score on the pre-test was compared with their score on the post-test to examine the impact of the intervention on their writing performance.

After that, the qualitative data obtained from the semi-structured interviews were analyzed according to the following steps. First, the research team read the transcripts carefully to familiarize themselves. During the reading process, if there was any confusion in the interviewees’ answers, the research team made phone calls to ask students to clarify. Then, all members would analyze all transcripts by coding excerpts and themes regarding why students had mean differences between pre-test and post-test for each feature in rubrics. After two weeks of qualitative data analysis, the research team gathered and compared their analyses. Breed analyses would be retained, and other analyzes would be reviewed with the assistance of an expert in qualitative data analysis. This person had demonstrated his ability to analyze qualitative data through his scientific work. With the support of the expert, the research team would discuss adjusting the analysis for differences among research team members.

Procedures

The study was conducted in three phases: pre-intervention, intervention, and post-intervention.

Pre-Intervention

During this phase, the research team conducted a literature review to develop a framework for the study. Besides, the analytic rubrics developed by many previous researchers would be systematized to select the most suitable one for this study. The result was analytic rubrics adapted from Jacobs et al. (1981), although old, was the most appropriate choice for the context of this study. After building the framework, the research team developed the data collection tools, tests, and main interview questions. At the same time, the research team contacted the administration of a foreign language school in Southwest Vietnam to ask for permission to conduct this study in a writing class they managed. With the approval of the headboard, the research team contacted three writing teachers teaching the essay writing module to recruit them to participate in the study as research collaborators as teachers in the experimental class. Of the three teachers contacted, one, named Mike, accepted, and the other two declined due to personal reasons. Therefore, Mike’s class was selected to experiment. The research team then talked to Mike about how they planned to research to ensure Mike understood his role in the research, how it would be done, and what the results would mean. With Mike’s consent, the team met with students to discuss and invite them to participate. Mike’s class had 22 English-major students who agreed to participate in this study voluntarily. Students were required to do a pre-test, as mentioned in the data collection instruments section. The research had officially moved into the experimental phase.

Intervention

The intervention lasted 17 weeks, and students would study 150 minutes each week, equivalent to three periods a week at this institution. Intervention was divided into two sub-phases, including two weeks for training students to use analytic rubrics and have knowledge of essay writing and 15 weeks of experimenting for students to use analytic rubrics to evaluate their peers’ performance.

During the two weeks of introducing students to analytic rubrics, Mike used writing samples, which were assessed, to be presented to students and evaluated against analytic rubrics. Mike then published the test scores and had the students compare their scores and ratings with the assessment of the sample papers. From there, Mike thoroughly explained the rubrics and why the samples were scored at that level. This two-week process

gave the research team complete confidence in the students' understanding of the analytic rubrics to be ready for the second phase of the experiment.

In phase two, Mike would use lesson plans prepared by the research team and strictly follow the plans' steps. Each plan has four steps according to the following structure: Warming up, Pre-writing, While-writing, and Post-writing. Warm-up activities, depending on the situation of each session, were used to help students focus on the lecture, introduce the lecture, or improve the classroom atmosphere. The pre-writing stage was used to provide learners with the topic of writing, the vocabulary, the grammatical points that could be used in the students' writing, and the structure of each article based on the function of the writing genres. Students would then be given a period of 40 minutes to write their papers. Finally, the writing would be exchanged for students to use the analysis rubrics and evaluate the work of their peers. Students would give marks and explain to their friends why the writing was graded that way. During the students' discussion, Mike would walk around the room, listening and checking to see if the students were using the analytic rubrics correctly. If wrong, Mike would correct it immediately for students to better their understanding of the rubrics.

Post-Intervention

After 15 weeks of learning to write and use analytic rubrics to evaluate their peers' writing, the intervention ended, and learners took the post-test. The impact of the intervention was analyzed using a Pair-sample t-test to see if there was a significant difference between the pre-test and the post-test results. Then, based on the results of each participant, the research team interviewed six students, in which, based on the mean difference, three students were said to have the most progressive and three students the least. The results are presented below.

Findings and Discussion

The results of the Pair-sample t-test used to compare the writing performance of students in the pre-test and post-test are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Writing performance comparison results between pre-test and post-test

Variables	Pre-test	Post-test	t-value	p-value
	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)		
Content	24.60 (2.68)	26.28 (1.92)	-4.38	.00
Organization	17.09 (1.81)	17.28 (1.44)	-.59	.56
Vocabulary	15.72 (1.08)	16.95 (1.13)	-3.70	.00
Language Use	19.30 (2.42)	21.78 (1.54)	-5.37	.00
Mechanics	4.36 (.52)	4.45 (.52)	-1.03	.31
Total	81.09 (7.78)	86.77 (5.99)	-4.82	.00

The results reveal a significant difference between pre-PA and post-PA on the total scores ($t=4.82$; $p=0.00$). The mean score for post-PA on total ($M = 86.77$) is significantly higher than that for pre-PA ($M = 81.09$). It indicated that students made significant progress when the practice of PA was being carried out. The learners enhanced their writing performance after using analytic rubrics to evaluate their peer writing.

The respective mean score for students' performance on each feature before the practice of analytic rubric for peer assessment was lower than that after the treatment. The results of paired samples t-test showed that there was a significant difference between Pre-PA and Post-PA on the sub-scores of content ($t=-4.38$; $p=.00$), vocabulary ($t=-3.70$; $p=.00$) and language use ($t=-5.37$; $p=.00$). It indicated that learners made significant progress in the aspect of content and language use of their compositions within the period when the practice of analytic rubric for peer-assessment.

In the data obtained from the interviews, some learners also confirmed the same thing. Specifically, David and Brian talked about how they developed the idea in their writing through participating in the intervention as follows,

"After reading my friend's post, I got more ideas about the topic. It is apparent in rubrics how the development of ideas affects the score. Moreover, I also know how to develop ideas more logically to avoid repeating or deviating from the topic. This is also an idea that I can get more points on content development in my writing. Since then, it has become so much better." (David)

"Reading other people's writing works helps me understand the topic more deeply. Since then, I have developed better ideas for my article. Besides, the way that good writers change ideas is also very interesting. I learned a lot. I compare it with the content grading criteria in rubrics. Thanks to that, I applied this knowledge to my test and got an unexpected result." (Brian)

It can be seen that the use of analytic rubrics in peer assessment helped students know how they could be assessed and, at the same time, learn what was good in their peers' writing. From there, they learned more and

wrote better with diverse ideas. The results were somewhat equivalent to the findings in previous studies (e.g., Wride, 2017; Spiller, 2012; Topping, 2017; Kvale, 2006; Boud&Falchikov, 2007), but they just focused on assessing the strengths of peer assessment. In this study, the analytic rubrics, through excerpts from David and Brian, also played an essential role in developing the content in the learners' writing.

Similarly, Emma and Elizabeth also talked about the strengths of using analytic rubrics in peer assessment for content development in their writing. In addition, they mentioned increasing their knowledge of language and vocabulary use after participating in the intervention. They said,

“Learning this way is so much fun. In addition to being able to develop ideas to my writing, I also learned how my friends used words and grammar. From there, I paraphrased another way in my work. This helps me a lot in presenting ideas linearly but without overlapping words.” (Emma)

“I learned a lot from my friends through using analytic rubrics to evaluate each other, know to what extent I know how to use word and structure types that can help me get a higher score. So, I often look up my friends' word use to see what level of the difficulty the word is, B1, B2, or higher. For difficult vocabulary words, I take notes and use them in my writing. This helped me a lot in the last test.” (Elizabeth)

Reading the others' work and giving assessments helped students develop their vocabulary and knowledge of English grammar. This has been demonstrated in previous studies (Ritonga et al., 2022; Mustafa & Yusuf, 2022). However, through Elizabeth's excerpt, this study shows that knowing the evaluation criteria would improve learners' learner autonomy. Not only did they rate their friend's work innocuously, but they also tested the word difficulty themselves to see how to achieve a high level, high score based on the evaluation criteria.

The test results also revealed no significant difference between pre-PA and post-PA on the sub-scales of organization ($t=-.59$; $p=.56$) and mechanics ($t=-1.03$; $p=.31$). In other words, students did not make significant progress in the organization and mechanics of their writing. During the interview, all interviewees agreed that using analytic rubrics to assess their peers did not change their understanding of organization and mechanics in writing. Brian and Emily said,

“Honestly, I did not pay much attention to the mechanics and organization of the article. Those points are not very important to me. Moreover, conversely, I rarely comment on these errors when reviewing my friend's writing.” (Brian)

“About the organization of each type of article, we have studied it very carefully, so it is rare for my friend and me to make a big mistake about it. So I ignored it when I commented on my friend's post. Similarly, the mechanics part is not too important. You know, the score for this section is not that great in rubrics, and it is usually a reflection of the carefulness of the writer. Therefore, I only make general comments while evaluating my friends' works. As for whether they are more careful, I think it depends on each person's personality.” (Emily)

In the study by Muhyiddin (2012), learners were commonly careless in writing the words and never edited their writing in terms of spelling. They rarely looked for word spelling in the dictionary when confronting difficult words. Also, they usually misused punctuation marks in their writing, such as full stops, commas, and semi-colons. Regarding capitalization, students did not seem to care about capital letters in writing activities and often ignored them. Darus and Ching (2009) declared that mechanics was one of the four most errors students frequently commit in writing. As a result, in this study, even though learners had their peers evaluate and give feedback on their written works, it was probable that those assessors did not pay lots of attention to give feedback on their peers' errors of punctuation, capitalization, or spelling. Additionally, Bing (2016) stated that teachers commonly emphasized aspects like sentence and paragraph writing, textual organization, rhetorical devices, etc., in traditional writing classes. All in all, the quality of mechanics did not attract a lot of learners' attention to be improved.

In addition to the above results, another significant result was found in this study. Specifically, in the data obtained from the interviews, the learners who did not succeed after participating in the intervention were most likely those who had good writing ability from the beginning. However, participating in the intervention did not bring high value to their development. Jennifer and Christopher explained,

“I think this is a pretty interesting form of assessment. I find it very meaningful to help my friends develop their skills through peer assessment. However, after reading their works, giving comments, and evaluating, I do not feel that I have learned too much from those works. For most of the points where they were weak, I got a pretty good rating before participating in the intervention. Maybe it would be better if I took the time to learn more difficult words....” (Jennifer)

“I learn a lot from the times I read good articles by those with good writing skills. However, I did not learn much from reading the articles of those who did not write well. Therefore, it would be better if this assessment method is used in a class where all learners are at the same level....” (Christopher)

Jennifer and Christopher are learners with very high pre-test scores, but their post-test performance is not as good. They mentioned that viewing articles that were not as good as theirs would allow them to help others but waste their time learning new knowledge for self-development. This is pretty different from the study of

Topping (2017), which indicated that equal-status peers would similarly impact all kinds of students. However, this study found a significant difference when the learners would grow faster if they were given the opportunity to work with people with equal or higher qualifications because they would learn a lot from their peers. On the contrary, working with inferior people would inhibit an individual's development. Therefore, the pairing of learners needs to be considered a lot.

Conclusion

The study was conducted to test the impact of training learners to use analytic rubrics for peer assessment on their writing ability. The results showed a positive impact of the intervention on learners' writing ability when the results of the post-test were significantly higher than the results of the pre-test. In particular, the students developed significantly in the content, vocabulary, and language use sections of their writing. In contrast, the intervention had no significant effect on the organization and mechanics of the learners' writing. Findings from the interview also partially explained the impact of the intervention on student progress. However, choosing interview participants based on mean difference also showed some unpredicted results. In particular, using analytic rubrics could have an excellent effect on people with poor writing ability in pre-test because they showed tremendous progress when working with learners with sufficient writing skills. However, the opposite did not happen. Specifically, learners with high scores in the pre-test did not make much progress, and even their writing skills were lower than they were at the beginning after participating in the intervention. The results partly concluded that analytic rubrics could be great for low- or medium-level learners but might not work well for learners with good writing abilities.

Implications

The current study showed the positive impact of training learners to use analytic rubrics to perform peer assessment on learners' writing ability. Therefore, it encourages English teachers to conduct this training for their learners in learning to write. However, teachers need to pay attention to the criteria in rubrics needed to be described very clearly to make sure that learners understand each criterion and adequately evaluate the writing ability of their peers. Besides, the pairing of learners also needs to be considered very carefully. This study has shown that matching learners with disparate abilities can bring good results for low-ability learners but negatively affect high-ability learners.

Learners also need to pay more attention to the criteria for evaluating their writing to meet the requirements and score as expected. Using analytic rubrics will provide insights into how writing is rated based on apparent criteria. From there, they properly assess their strengths and weaknesses to improve their writing skills gradually.

Limitations and Recommendations for Further Studies

This study explains the impact of the intervention on learners' writing ability. However, it has not demonstrated the optimization of the intervention compared with other assessment methods. Therefore, the following studies should conduct experiments comparing different evaluation methods. Moreover, this study has not demonstrated the impact of the intervention on learners with different writing abilities. Therefore, the following studies should divide participants based on their ability to test the effectiveness of the intervention on each type of learner.

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Appendices

EXPLANATION ESSAYS

By the end of this lesson, you will able to:

- understand the format of an essay,
- use five techniques to write hooks,
- write a complete explanation essay.

Time allotted (150 minutes)	Teacher's activities	Students' activities
10 minutes	Warm-up and lead-in Activity 1: Ask students about their days Activity 2: Have them ask one another using the question word 'Why?'	Ask and answer the questions
5 minutes	Pre-writing Activity 3: Ask students to look at the pictures and list out the reasons why students work part-time	Work in pairs and discuss the reasons why students work part-time
10 minutes	Activity 4: Ask students to form groups of 3 or 4, discuss and write their ideas	Work in groups, share and write ideas on the board
10 minutes	Activity 5: Introduce five techniques to write a hook by showing five statements and ask them to match each statement to the technique. A. "Whenever you are asked if you can do a job, tell 'Certainly I can!' Then get busy and find out how to do it", stated Theodore Roosevelt. B. Why are so many students working part-time? C. Working part-time has become a phenomenon among university students in Vietnam, and Can Tho University students follow this trend as well. D. For most students, working part-time is like a game: they do it if it is fun and stop it when it is stressful. E. A survey conducted in 2015 indicated that more than 50% of Can Tho University students worked part-time. 1. An eye-catching statement 2. A surprising statistic 3. A quotation 4. A general truth 5. A question	Read the hooks and figure out what the technique is used for writing each hook
5 minutes	Activity 6: Show the incomplete definition of a hook and ask students to complete it Hook is the _____ sentence of an essay aiming to • catch readers' _____ • by _____ introducing the topic. <i>Key: first, attention, interestingly</i>	Complete the definition
15 minutes	Activity 7: Show students a sample introduction and ask them to name the other two sentences after the hook <i>Working part-time has become a phenomenon among university students in Vietnam, and Cantho University students follow this trend as well. Although it is believed to cause some trouble relating to time management, many students find it very beneficial. Actually, an increasing number of students are interested in taking part-time jobs in order to relieve parents' financial pressure, learn some more skills and make the most of their spare time.</i> Key: Connecting sentence and Thesis statement	Work in groups and name the other two sentences in the introduction
15 minutes	Activity 8: Arrange these words/phrases to have complete topic sentences in body paragraphs <i>A topic sentence = The topic + A controlling idea</i> 1. First /, attend university / many students / to study / in depth / a particular subject /. 2. Another common reason / is that / for going to university / a college education often / in the future / leads to a better career /. 3. Finally, / making friends and enjoying an active social life / for some students, / for another four years / can be a sufficient reason to stay in	

15 minutes	<p>school /.</p> <p>Key:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. First, many students attend university to study a particular subject in depth. [...] 2. Another common reason for going to university is that a college education often leads to a better career in the future. [...] 3. Finally, for some students, making friends and enjoying an active social life can be a sufficient reason to stay in school for another four years. [...] <p>Activity 9: Ask students to write a topic sentence for the body paragraph in pairs</p> <p>..... . A four-year studying process is long enough to make students realize that they must have an income to partly afford to their university life. They should not keep asking their parents who have been back-breaking at work for their children's future. Therefore, a sum of money from part-time jobs somewhat lessens the money-based stress.</p> <p>Activity 10: Ask students to order the sentences to form a well-organised paragraph and complete their answers in groups</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Regardless of the reasons, students should remember why they are in university and do their best to achieve their goals. 2. In conclusion, there are many different reasons for students to go to university. 3. These reasons can be exploring their favorite academic fields, gaining an advantage in the job market in the future, or meeting people with different backgrounds to develop friendships. <p>Key: In conclusion, there are many different reasons for students to go to university. These reasons can be exploring their favorite academic fields, gaining an advantage in the job market in the future, or meeting people with different backgrounds to develop friendships. Regardless of the reasons, students should remember why they are in university and do their best to achieve their goals</p>	<p>Write complete topic sentences</p> <p>Work in pairs to write a topic sentence</p> <p>Form a paragraph and share it with group mates</p>
40 minutes	<p>While-writing</p> <p>Activity 11: Write a well-organized essay to explain why</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. some youngsters are crazy about K-pop or Western music instead of traditional one. 2. many people have a tendency to eat fast food nowadays. 3. some students choose to study abroad. 4. young people are interested in foreign films rather than domestic ones. 5. most Vietnamese men like to drink beer/alcohol. 6. Vietnamese people love football 7. more and more young people are getting addicted to social networks. 8. country people migrate to big cities 	<p>Write a complete essay individually</p>
20 minutes	<p>Asks students to exchange their essays with other classmates to check by using the rubrics.</p>	<p>Check the essay</p>

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